

Assessing the scalar potential distribution produced by a floating leader using the Finite Element Method

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Abstract — This work proposes an implementation of the Kasemir’s bidirectional bipolar leader concept using the Finite Element Method (FEM) to study the electric field levels at the tip of grounded structures produced by thunderclouds and lightning leaders. The goal of this implementation is to compare the preliminary results with those obtained applying the Charge Simulation Method (CSM), which presents some modelling limitations that can be critical when it comes to the evaluation of electric field levels at the tip of grounded structures. From the comparison between the obtained results under the use of both methods, the main conclusions are drawn, namely: the FEM can be successfully used with the support of a friendly interface, such as Ansys Maxwell software; the obtained results for the main study case are similar to those corresponding to the CSM implementation; the electric field levels at the surface of charged objects can be evaluated consistently.

Keywords— Finite element method, charge simulation method, bipolar leader concept, electric field produced by thunderclouds and lightning leaders.

I. INTRODUCTION

The electric field level at the tip of grounded structures plays a relevant role in the definition of the cloud-to-ground (CG) lightning strike point [1]. When this electric field exceeds the local dielectric strength, strong ionization processes take place, further resulting in the launching of an upward leader [2]. The sooner the upward leader is launched, the higher the probability of connection to the downward leader.

For the case of a vertical downward leader propagating above the tip of a grounded structure, several factors can contribute to the early initiation of an upward leader, two of them standing out as the most relevant ones: the charge distribution along the downward leader and the structure height. In this context, determining at which height a specific charge distribution along the downward leader can trigger the initiation of an upward leader in a grounded structure is of utmost importance for computing the extension of its exposure area.

Under the perspective of the Electrogeometric Model (EGM) [3], the level of exposure (or attractiveness) of grounded structures is usually quantified by the so-called attractive radius, for a free-standing structure whose plan-view dimensions are considerably smaller than its height, or by the attractive swath (or shadow zone), for a straight horizontally extended structure, such as power lines [4]. In general, the distance between the downward leader tip and the grounded structure when there is a high probability of attachment is defined as striking distance [5], and this parameter is directly related to the attractive zone of the object to be struck.

Several equations have been proposed in literature for determining the striking distance, most of them applying the form of (1). In this context, the correlation experimentally observed between I_p (the prospective return stroke peak current, which, in turn, presents a correlation with the total transferred charge) and SD (striking distance) is calibrated by empirical values of constants A and b . Table 1 summarizes A and b values proposed by several authors.

$$SD = AI_p^b \quad (1)$$

TABLE I. COEFFICIENTS OF EQ. (1)

Authors	A	b
Young et al. [6]	27,0	0,32
Armstrong and Whitehead [7]	6,0	0,80
Brown and Whitehead [8]	6,4	0,75
Love [9]	10,0	0,65
Cooray et al. [5]	1,9	0,90

A comprehensive assessment of the influence that the charge distribution along the leader exerts on the electric field level at ground has been performed in [5]. According to their evaluations, the authors verified significant variation on the striking distance when different charge distributions were considered.

In this regard, this work intends to present a contribution moving forward the developments presented in [10], which comprises the study of lightning striking distance from the determination of electric field levels at the tip of grounded structures produced by lightning leaders whose charge distributions are physically consistent with the ambient potential developed by the thunderclouds. The adopted leader model is the one implemented by Mazur and Ruhnke [11], by means of the Charge Simulation Method (CSM) [12], according to the bipolar leader concept of the ground-breaking work developed by Kasemir [13]. As a novel contribution, this paper proposes the use of the Finite Element Method (FEM) to assess the scalar potential and corresponding electric field levels produced by thunderclouds and lightning leaders, instead of applying the Charge Simulation Method, to overcome the limitations of the latter.

It is known that CSM relies on simplified geometries or regular arrangements of charges, which may not accurately represent real scenarios [12]. Moreover, the effect of proximity can impact the accuracy and reliability of the results provided by CSM, mainly when the electric field at the surface of charged objects (such as grounded structures) is considered.

On the other hand, the Finite Element Method is a versatile numerical technique that can handle irregular and complex geometries by dividing them into smaller elements, allowing for accurate representation and analysis [14]. This flexibility is especially useful when dealing with non-uniform charge distributions or complex structures, such as those associated with grounded objects under the influence of lightning leaders.

To accomplish the proposed goal, this paper is organized as follows. After this brief introduction, the main theoretical aspects related to the model adopted to study electric field produced by lightning events are discussed in Section II. The methodology to validate the use of the FEM is described in Section III. In Section IV, the preliminary results that compare the application of CSM and FEM are discussed. Finally, some final remarks are presented in Section V.

II. THE BIPOLAR LEADER MODEL IMPLEMENTED BY MAZUR AND RUNHKE

According to the theory first presented by Kasemir in [15], the intense electric field inside the thunderclouds, along with some secondary process (such as the incidence of cosmic rays) [4], give rise to local floating plasma leaders. Since these leaders are originated from an “electrodeless discharge”, the charges released during the ionization process tend to be stored around the plasma body according to the electric field orientation, resulting in a bipolar leader with zero net charge. The natural tendency of charge accumulation at the extremities of the leader intensifies the local electric field, which contributes to the leader extension process. For those cases in which one of the leader’s extremities propagates toward the ground, an upward leader in protruding grounded structures might be initiated, which can cause the connection of both leaders, leading ultimately to the return stroke process.

A first numerical implementation of this concept was presented in [11] using the Charge Simulation Method. From a cylindrical thundercloud model, which is reproduced in Fig. 1, Mazur and Ruhnke applied an electrostatic approach to study the conditions for the initiation and development of intracloud and cloud-to-ground lightning. It was verified that the electric field levels are more intense in the regions between charge centers of opposite polarities, i.e., at 5-km and 9-km

altitudes. In this regard, if a plasma leader is initiated at 9 km, an intracloud discharge occurs; however, if the initial breakdown occurs at 5 km, a negative downward lightning flash will be observed. In their implementation, Mazur and Ruhnke also assumed the leader to be a perfect cylindrical conductor of 1-m radius, whose corresponding potential is approximately equal to the average cloud potential along its length.

The development of a cloud-to-ground negative lightning according to Mazur and Ruhnke is described in the following lines. After the initiation of the bipolar leader at a 5-km altitude, it develops bidirectionally along the axis of symmetry of the cloud, with an average speed to both directions of 10^5 m/s. As the leader extends, its potential changes, according to the background potential of the cloud. The progression of its upper extremity, which is filled with positive charges, ceases when its potential reaches the same level of the local background potential. From this time on, only the lower extremity propagates, filled with negative charges. When the lower extremity of the bipolar leader hits the ground, its highly negative potential shifts to zero, giving rise to the return stroke current. Thus, during this process, extra positive charges are induced along the leader so that this zero-potential condition of the channel is achieved [10].

Fig. 1. Thundercloud model composed of four regions of different charge densities: two main charge regions with +50 C (0.212 nC/m³) and -80 C (-0.147 nC/m³) and two secondary regions with -10 C (-3.183 nC/m³) and +3 C (1.273 nC/m³). [10]

As briefly described, all the stages of leader propagation can be consistently explained by the solid physical foundation of Kasemir’s bipolar leader concept. From the numerical implementation presented by Mazur and Ruhnke, the relation between the thundercloud potential and the charges stored along the leader can be further assessed, so that one can estimate the conditions for the initiation of upward leaders on grounded structures.

III. THE PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The evaluation of the electric field levels just above the tip of grounded structures using the Charge Simulation Method is subject to inaccuracy and uncertainties, mainly due to the proximity effect. Depending on the criteria for the upward leader initiation [16], these limitations may have a great impact on the analysis to be developed. Thus, this work proposes the use of the Ansys Maxwell software [17], which is FEM based, to evaluate the electric field produced at the tip of grounded structures during the approximation of lightning leaders, to overcome the intrinsic limitations of CSM.

The implementation in both methods (FEM and CSM) of the thundercloud model of Fig. 1 is proposed, so that the results can be compared, and the application of the FEM can be validated. The same conditions for leader propagations are adopted and the scalar potential is calculated along the propagating leader. The minimum required extent of the calculation region was also assessed to avoid computation overhead.

For the case of the CSM implementation, the scalar potential at any point z along the cloud vertical axis, $V(z)$, was obtained from the Coulomb's Law (2), considering a uniform volume charge density, ρ_v , for all the regions illustrated in Fig. 1; dv' stands for the differential charge volume of the charge centers, and R is the distance between each volume element and the point z . This integral can be solved either analytically or numerically.

$$V(z) = \frac{1}{4\pi\epsilon_0} \iiint_{v'} \frac{\rho_v}{R} dv' \quad (2)$$

The analytical solution of (2) is presented in (3), in which r_{int} , r_{ext} , h_{inf} and h_{sup} stands for the following dimensions of the cloud charge center, respectively: internal radius, external radius, base height, and top height.

$$V(z) = \frac{\rho_v}{4\epsilon_0} \left[u \sqrt{u^2 + r_{int}^2} + r_{int}^2 \ln \left| u + \sqrt{u^2 + r_{int}^2} \right| - u \sqrt{u^2 + r_{ext}^2} - r_{ext}^2 \ln \left| u + \sqrt{u^2 + r_{ext}^2} \right| \right] \Big|_{u=z-h_{inf}}^{u=z-h_{sup}} \quad (3)$$

The Charge Simulation Method itself was applied to calculate the charges stored along the leader during each step of the simulation, as well as to calculate the resulting scalar potential along the vertical axis of the thundercloud ($0 \leq z \leq 25 \text{ km}$). The representation of the leader was carried out according to the implementation presented in [11]. A vertical line of charges spaced by 1 m represented the leader at each simulation step. The magnitudes of these charges were calculated considering the potential at a 1-m distance from the z -axis equal to the average cloud potential of the region taken up by the leader.

The first implementation of the thundercloud and leader models on Ansys Maxwell required no code development, given the friendly interface of this software. However, for further developments, for which several thundercloud dimensions will be considered to contemplate different magnitudes of total transferred charge (and, thus, several peak currents), scripts are expected to be developed to automate the calculations.

Fig. 2 shows the thundercloud model drawn on Ansys Maxwell. The leader development was also simulated in 10 steps, from its initiation inside the cloud until the attachment to the ground. The leader was modeled as a 1-m radius hollow cylinder, composed by a perfect conductor material. The propagation features are the same of the CSM simulations, i.e., 500-m extensions of both leader extremities with corresponding speed of 10^5 m/s . Fig. 3 illustrates the leader's position and length in the 7th simulation step.

Fig. 2. Thundercloud model drawn on Ansys Maxwell [17]

Fig. 3. Leader extension (red vertical thin line) at the 7th simulation step

Finally, to demonstrate the applicability of this approach in the evaluation of the lightning exposure area of ordinary structures, a common building represented by a perfect conductor cuboid whose dimensions are $10 \text{ m} \times 10 \text{ m} \times 30 \text{ m}$ (length, width, and height) was considered to assess the electric field levels produced by lightning leaders, as illustrated in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. An ordinary building simulated in Ansys Maxwell

IV. PRELIMINARY RESULTS

Fig. 5 presents the potential and electric field magnitude produced by the thundercloud along the vertical axis of the cloud, obtained from the application of the Charge Simulation Method. These results are practically the same as those presented by Mazur and Ruhnke in [11]. It can be noted that, from ground level up to 10 km, the scalar potential is negative, which indicates a dominant contribution from the negative charge centers. However, as higher altitudes are considered, the scalar potential becomes positive. In terms of the electric field level, a corresponding polarity behavior can be identified. Furthermore, the most intense electric field

levels are found in the altitudes between different charge centers, namely at 5 and 9 km.

One might speculate that the maximum E-field levels plotted in Fig. 5 are much lower than the dielectric strength of the atmospheric air, which is indeed correct. Nevertheless, recall that other processes have already been detected as responsible for contributing to the leader initiation process, such as cosmic rays [1], [18]. As the model does not consider the corona space charges near the ground, a considerable electric field level is observed at low altitudes, remarkably at ground level, due to the disregard of the corona layer attenuation effect.

Fig. 5. Scalar potential (left panel) and vertical electric field (right panel) produced by the thundercloud along its vertical axis, resulting from the application of the Charge Simulation Method (CSM).

Fig. 6 illustrates the potential profile produced by the development of the cloud-to-ground leader, as it progressively propagates toward the ground. One can note that, at each step, the potential profile along the leader is uniform and it suddenly shifts to the ambient potential (produced by the thundercloud) just ahead of each extremity. Furthermore, as the scalar potential of the leader was considered to be the average value of the cloud ambient potential along the taken-up length, its value is displaced rightward (i.e., it becomes less negative) when longer lengths are considered. Another important physical aspect of the leader propagation is that the extension of the upper extremity can no longer occur through 500-m steps after the 7th step, since in that region the leader potential is very close to the ambient scalar potential, i. e., no conditions for further leader propagation are fulfilled anymore.

Fig. 6. Vertical scalar potential profile ($0 \leq z \leq 10 \text{ km}$) produced by the thundercloud and 10 successive leader propagation steps, resulting from the application of the Charge Simulation Method (CSM).

The scalar potential at any point of the considered region can be also easily evaluated, so that the electric field can be determined everywhere. However, since the main goal of this paper is to present only a preliminary comparison between the CSM and FEM results, such an evaluation is intended to be carried out in future works.

Fig. 7 presents the results of the first evaluations carried out using the FEM-based Ansys Maxwell software, which comprise the assessment of the requirements of the extent of the calculation region. This is necessary for defining the minimum distance from the cloud vertical axis that the boundary conditions need to be placed in order not to influence the results. It was observed that a 15-km radius cylindrical region was the thinnest one capable of producing results like those provided by the CSM. In this regard, radius shorter than this value produced more intense scalar potential levels, because the boundary conditions significantly affected the results. However, as expected, regions with radii greater than this critical value did not present different results but implied in greater computational effort. Thus, for the sake of conservativeness, the results presented from now on were obtained with a 20-km radius calculation region.

Fig. 7. Scalar potential produced by the thundercloud along its vertical axis, resulting from the application of the Finite Element Method (FEM) with different computation regions.

Fig. 8 shows the computed scalar potential along the cloud axis for the 10 leader steps before it touches the ground. One can note that the results are very similar to those presented in Fig. 6, which reinforce the adoption of an averaged potential for the floating leader.

Fig. 8. Vertical scalar potential profile ($0 \leq z \leq 10 \text{ km}$) produced by the thundercloud and 10 successive leader propagation steps, resulting from the application of the the Finite Element Method (FEM).

V. FINAL REMARKS

The slight variations observed between the curves of Figs. 6 and 8 will be further investigated in future works. The authors consider that they can be related to the differences between the nature of numerical methods, CSM and FEM. Nevertheless, the similarity of the physical behavior of both sets of curves (CSM and FEM) is consistent with the theoretical aspects of Kasemir's bipolar leader concept.

A rehearsal on the assessment of the effects produced at the top of grounded structures under the influence of the thundercloud depicted in Fig. 1 is presented in Fig. 9, which comprises the scalar potential along the cloud axis for several conditions of leader propagation above a perfect-conductor cuboid whose dimensions are $10\text{ m} \times 10\text{ m} \times 30\text{ m}$ (length, width, and height). Fig. 9b presents a zoomed view of Fig. 9a.

Fig. 9. Vertical scalar potential profile ($0 \leq z \leq 10\text{ km}$) produced by the thundercloud and 10 successive leader propagation steps, resulting from the application of the the Finite Element Method (FEM).

Since the grounded element was considered to be composed by a perfectly conducting surface, as lower altitudes are considered, the ambient potential transitions from the leader potential to zero. As this transition occurs more abruptly when the lower extremity of the bipolar leader is closer to the ground, the electric field at the top of the cuboid becomes more intense. This information can be used to estimate the electric field at the top of the structure and, thus, to determine when an upward leader is expected to be launched. For this specific condition, the exposure area of the cuboid can be assessed.

This paper presented a preliminary analysis of the application of the Finite Element Method to assess the modelling of the bipolar leader associated to a cloud to ground lightning. The same model adopted by Mazur and Ruhnke [11] of the bidirectional bipolar leader model [13] was implemented in the FEM-based software Ansys Maxwell and the results of scalar potential as the leader develops were compared with those derived from the classical application of the Charge Simulation Method. The obtained results presented the same physical behavior, which validate the performed implementation.

In future works, the authors intend to assess the quality of the modelling by evaluating the degree of reduction of the proximity effect when the FEM implementation is compared with the CSM. The purpose of this study is to further discuss the use of a FEM-based software to evaluate the lightning electric fields produced at the surface of grounded structures, in order to determine their lightning exposure area and the influence of their own height and shape in terms of lightning incidence.

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